

GPS collar data from free ranging sheep in Norway: New knowledge for farmers, authorities and researchers

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About 45% of the land area of Norway can provide feed resources for grazing domestic ruminants and can be described as unfenced rangeland forest and mountain land. They provide summer grazing feed and it is estimated that this feed has a value of some NOK 1000 million annually. In general, these systems are considered to provide high levels of animal welfare as animals can express natural behaviour in. However, this is compromised by losses to predators as well as disease and accidents. A main challenge for sheep farmers is the supervision and guarding of these animals. This challenge is the background for the extensive implementation of GPS collars on grazing livestock in Norway in order to track animals during the grazing season. It is estimated that currently some 150 000 GPS collars are on sheep in Norway and they are gathering about 100 million positions every year; with number of collars as well as quality and quantity data improving every year. The farm grazing group of Meråker beitelag consists of 25 farmers that graze some 2000 ewes with lambs every year. All ewes have GPS tracking collars and since 2019 position data are gathered every 4th hour throughout the grazing season. A large proportion of the farmers also use the Norwegian Sheep Recording System (NSRS) for farm management, where performance, pedigree and health data is recorded. Merging GPS data with performance data from NSRS allows the study of numerous factors in the development of Early Warning Systems (EWS) related sheep health and welfare (i.e. surveillance of mastitis, other disease, predators, climate, vegetation etc). Also, land use knowledge is important in a future of increasing multi interest conflicts from the society in these areas (i.e. cabins, hiking, hunting, windmills etc.).